

Formal Description of the Correspondence Between Theodor W. Adorno and Hans G Helms 1957-1968

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Authority Records of the Correspondence Authors

Adorno, Theodor W. (1903-1969): VIAF <http://viaf.org/viaf/95247377>; GND <https://d-nb.info/gnd/118500775>

Adorno, Gretel (1902-1993): VIAF <http://viaf.org/viaf/76383955>; GND <https://d-nb.info/gnd/104750820>

Helms, Hans G (1932-2012): VIAF <http://viaf.org/viaf/61719073>; GND <https://d-nb.info/gnd/122357620>

Formal Description

The correspondence between Hans G Helms and Theodor W. Adorno, conducted in German, lasted from 1957 to 1968. It was initiated by Helms on July 18, 1957, and concluded with a letter from Helms dated July 14, 1968. Some administrative letters or letters sent while Adorno was absent were signed by his secretaries, Elfriede Olbrich and L. Herschel. In 1958, Gretel Adorno and Helms corresponded regarding the publication of writings from Walter Benjamin's estate. After Theodor W. Adorno's death on August 6, 1969, Helms continued to correspond with Gretel Adorno until September 9, 1969.

Both authors have archived both the carbon copies of the letters they sent and the letters, postcards, and manuscripts they received. The majority of the correspondence consists of typewritten letters or their carbon copies. Handwritten texts are present only in exceptional cases, such as postcards. These documents were archived as part of the estates by the Theodor W. Adorno Archive and the Zentral- und Landesbibliothek Berlin. For the postcards and several letters, there are no carbon copies or other records on the sender's or recipient's side. The correspondence between Helms and Gretel Adorno in 1969 is documented only in Helms's estate. Since the institutions holding the collections have not yet exchanged copies of the missing letters in their collections, it is currently only possible to gain a complete picture of the correspondence by examining both estates. The following complete chronological list of all items in the correspondence allows one to identify the gaps in the two estates.

The correspondence documents preserved in Adorno's estate have been cataloged by the Theodor W. Adorno Archive under the call number TWAA Br 588 and are available to researchers. The estate is owned by the Hamburger Stiftung zur Förderung von Wissenschaft und Kultur. The finding aid entry is available at the following permalink and includes indexes of people, subjects, and works: <https://archiv.adk.de/objekt/2573046> According to the entry, the correspondence comprises a

total of 117 sheets: 38 letters and one postcard from Helms to Adorno, and 28 letters from Adorno to Helms. Among the 117 pages is a 14-page manuscript excerpt belonging to TWAA Br 588/10-27 from Helms's work *Fa:m' Ahniesgwow*, which at that time still bore the working title *Imre Ahniesgwow*. The other manuscripts sent by Helms to Adorno are cataloged separately in the Third-Party Manuscripts section:

- TWAA Mk 27, 1959-1964, <https://archiv.adk.de/objekt/3089432>
- TWAA Mk 98, <https://archiv.adk.de/objekt/3187839>
- TWAA Mk 179, *Untersuchung einiger zeitgenössischer Literatur nebst Diagnose und Krankheitsgeschichte*, autumn 1960, <https://archiv.adk.de/objekt/3250725>
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The documents from Helms's correspondence with Theodor and Gretel Adorno, preserved in his estate, have been cataloged by the Zentral- und Landesbibliothek Berlin (ZLB) under the call numbers Hel2-A125 through Hel2-A211 and are available to researchers in the ZLB's Berlin Collections. The rights holder is Dr. Susanne Willems. The catalog entry is available at the following permalink: <http://kalliope-verbund.info/DE-611-HS-2661435> According to the entry, the correspondence consists of a total of 106 sheets. The last document, cataloged under the call number Hel2-A211, is a newspaper article from the *Kölner Stadtanzeiger* dated September 21, 1988, titled "Adorno als Komponist" which was likely added to the correspondence by Helms.

An error occurred during cataloging regarding the letter listed under Hel2-A125. According to the carbon copy, Helms had dated it 44[sic].4.1956, which is why the ZLB considered it the first letter in the correspondence. However, Helms must have made a mistake not only in the date of the day but also in the year—likely a transposed digit: 1956 instead of the correct 1965. Both the salutation and the content leave no doubt that the two were already acquainted with one another. Given the reference to the third volume of Adorno's *Noten zur Literatur*, published in 1965, and Helms's request for information about Hans Mayer's essay on authority and the family, the letter was most likely written in April 1965. The letter is not found in Adorno's estate. But Adorno's reply dated April 21, 1965, refers to it, so it can be assumed that he received it.

List of Correspondence Items and Concordance of Signatures

Date (yyyy-mm-dd)	Author	Recipient	Type	TWAA Br	ZLB	Pages	Remarks
1957-07-18	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/1	Hel2- A126	1	
1957-07-22	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/2	Hel2- A127	1	
1957-08-19	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/3	Hel2- A128	1	
1957-08-27	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A129	1	

1957-09-15	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	-	Hel2- A130	1	
1957-09-17	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/4	Hel2- A131	1	
1957-09-21	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/5-8	Hel2- A132	4	
1957-09-27	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/9	Hel2- A133	1	
1958-08-20	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter and excer pt	588/10-27	Hel2- A134	17	Pages 13 to 27 excerpt of Imre Ahniesgwo w. The excerpt is not included in Hel2- A134.
1958-09-26	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/28	Hel2- A135	1	
1958-11-23	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/29	Hel2- A137	1	
1958-11-23	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Gretel	Letter	588/30	Hel2- A136	1	
1958-12-01	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/31-32	Hel2- A138	2	
1958-12-06	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/33-34	Hel2- A139	2	
1958-12-15	Adorno, Gretel	Helms, Hans G	Regist ered Letter	-	Hel2- A140	1	
1958-12-19	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/35-36	Hel2- A141	2	
1958-12-23	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/37-38	Hel2- A142	2	
1958-12-28	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/39-42	Hel2- A143	4	
1959-01-10	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/43	Hel2- A144	1	

1959-02-27	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/44-46	Hel2- A145	3	
1959-06-12	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/47	Hel2- A146	1	
1959-06-15	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A147	2	
1959-07-14	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/48	Hel2- A148	1	
1959-07-20	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/49	Hel2- A149	1	
1959-08-23	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Regist ered letter	588/50	Hel2- A150	1	Accompan ying manuscript of F:am' Ahniesgwo w
1959-08-24	Adorno, Theodor W. (Hersche l, L.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A151	1	
1959-11-16	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/51	Hel2- A152	1	
1959-11-21	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/52	Hel2- A153	1	
1959-12-04	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/53	Hel2- A154	1	
No date; [end of 1959]	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/54-55	-	2	
1960-01-11	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/56-57	Hel2- A155	2	
1960-02-27	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/58	Hel2- A156	1	
1960-03-29	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/59	Hel2- A157	1	
1960-04-19	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/60	Hel2- A158	1	

1960-05-09	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/61	Hel2- A159	1	
1960-06-15	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A160	1	
1960-08-01	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Express Letter	588/62	Hel2- A161	1	
1960-08-05	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A162	2	
1960-08-20	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/63	Hel2- A163	1	
1960-09-12	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/64-65	Hel2- 164	2	
1960-10-07	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/66	Hel2- A165	1	
1960-10-20	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A166	1	
1960-10-21	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A167	1	
1960-12-22	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/67-69	Hel2- A168	3	
1961-01-03	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/70-71	Hel2- A169	2	
1961-01-04	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/72	Hel2- A170	1	
1961-01-09	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Express letter	588/73-74	Hel2- A171	2	

1961-02-01	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/75	Hel2- A172	1	
1961-06-21	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/76	Hel2- A173	1	
1961-06-22	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/77	Hel2- A174	1	
1961-07-04	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A175	1	
1961-07-09	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Regist ered letter	588/78-79	Hel2- A176	2	
1961-07-19	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/80	Hel2- A177	1	
1961-08-06	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Regist ered letter	588/81	Hel2- A178	1	
1961-08-16	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Postc ard	-	Hel2- A179	-	
1962-12-23	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Regist ered letter	588/82	Hel2- A180	1	
1963-09-19	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/83-84	Hel2- A181	2	
1963-11-28	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/85-86	Hel2- A183 [sic]	2	Chronologi cally mistaken signature at Hel2.
1963-12-10	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/87-89	Hel2- A182 [sic]	3	Chronologi cally mistaken signature at Hel2.
1963-12-12	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A184	1	

1964-04-10	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Registered Letter	588/90-91	Hel2- A185	2	
1964-06-02	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/92	Hel2- A186	1	
1964-06-04	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/93-94	Hel2- A187	2	
1964-07-05	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Registered letter	588/95-96	Hel2- A188	2	
1964-07-27	Adorno, Theodor W. (Olbrich, E.)	Helms, Hans G	Letter	-	Hel2- A189	1	
1964-08-18	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Registered letter	588/97-99	Hel2- A190	3	
1964-08-25	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/100	Hel2- A191	1	
1964-09-10	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/101-103	Hel2- A192	3	
1964-09-23	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Registered Letter	588/104	Hel2- A193	1	
1964-10-07	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/105	Hel2- A194	1	
1964-10-14	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	-	Hel2- A195	1	
1964-12-21	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/106-107	Hel2- A196	2	
Incorrect original Date: 1956-04 -44 Presumed date: 1965-04	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	-	Hel2- A125	1	Because of content and context it is likely that this letter was written in April 1965.
1965-04-21	Adorno, Theodor	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/108	Hel2- A197	1	

	W.						
1965-05-06	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/109	Hel2- A198	1	
1966-10-15	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	-	Hel2- A199	1	
1966-10-26	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/110	Hel2- A200	1	
1966-11-05	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/111	Hel2- A201	1	
1966-11-07	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/112	Hel2- A202	1	
1966-11-13	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/113	Hel2- A203	1	
1966-12-31	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Postc ard	588/114 and 114v	-	-	
1968-06-30	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/115	Hel2- A204	1	
1968-07-02	Adorno, Theodor W.	Helms, Hans G	Letter	588/116	Hel2- A205	1	
1968-07-14	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Theodor W.	Letter	588/117	Hel2- A206	1	
1969-08-09	Adorno, Gretel	Helms, Hans G	Obitu ary, Machi ne printe d card	-	Hel2- A207	-	
1969-08-10	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Gretel	Letter	-	Hel2- A208	2	
1969-08	Adorno, Gretel	Helms, Hans G	Machi ne printe d card; additi onal hand writte n greeti	-	Hel2- A209	-	

			ngs				
1969-09-12	Helms, Hans G	Adorno, Gretel	Letter	-	Hel2- A210	1	Accompanying book ,Fetisch Revolution ,